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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) is a 6.5m infrared-optimized space telescope slated for launch early in the next decade and poised to hugely impact, for decades to come, all fields of astrophysics. Equipped with four unique scientific instruments providing a wide variety of imaging and spectroscopic capabilities covering the wavelength range from 0.6 to 28 microns, JWST will provide unprecedented sensitivity for probing the early Universe, understand galaxy assembly/evolution, study protoplanetary systems, probe the atmosphere of a wide variety of exoplanets and establish the potential habitability of Earth-like temperate worlds. This paper provides a brief overview of the JWST mission along with a few highlights of Canadian science programs. Two decades after initiating the development of this powerful space observatory through an international partnership led by the United States, in collaboration with Europe and Canada, the core scientific mission of JWST remains relevant and unchallenged by existing facilities. JWST is a pivotal reference mission for guiding the development of future flagship international space-based observatories as well as giant ground-based telescopes. JWST should be financially-supported by CSA for its entire lifetime with appropriate resources devoted to Education and Public Outreach.

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1 Introduction

After over three decades of planning and development ([Illingworth, 2016](#)), the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) is finally nearing completion and is currently slated for launch in the Spring of 2021. Led by NASA, with major contributions from the Canadian Space Agency (CSA) and the European Space Agency (ESA), this large 6.5m infrared telescope, successor to the successful Hubble and Spitzer Space Telescopes, is poised to revolutionise all fields of astrophysics, from probing the early Universe, to understanding galaxy assembly/evolution, to studying proto-planetary systems, to probing the atmosphere of a wide variety of exoplanets, to establishing the potential habitability of Earth-like temperate worlds. JWST is arguably one of the most complex machines currently under construction by humanity.

While the precious fruits of this historical scientific mission have yet to be harvested, one can already qualify Canada's participation in JWST as one of its greatest success stories in astrophysics. Canada's contribution to JWST will not only position Canadian astronomers at the forefront of many scientific breakthroughs, it has already strongly contributed to Canada's excellence and credibility for the development of space hardware. Canada's involvement in JWST was made possible thanks to significant financial commitment from the CSA (~\$180 millions up to now) but also from the united voice of the Canadian astronomical community who systematically ranked JWST first among space-based observatory facilities during the last two decadal Long Range Plans (LRPs). As we will soon enter the exciting phase of scientific operations, support for JWST in Canada remains crucial to fully capitalise on our investment, especially in the context of a potential extended mission that could keep JWST operational for more than a decade after launch.

This white paper provides a brief overview of the JWST mission, its status along with a few highlights of its main science drivers including some key Canadian projects to be executed as part of the Guaranteed Time Observations (GTO) and Early Release Science (ERS) programs. We highlight the importance of the JWST mission for the development of astrophysics in Canada as well as for future Canadian participation in major space-astronomy missions. We also discuss the need for an Education and Public Outreach strategy to maximize the visibility of both CSA and Canadian JWST science to the public.

A detailed description of the JWST mission is given in [Gardner et al. \(2006\)](#). There is also ample online material on the following web sites: [NASA](#), [Space Telescope Science Institute \(STScI\)](#), [ESA](#) and [CSA](#). A time exposure calculator and various tools for preparing JWST proposals are extensively documented in the [JWST User Documentation Home](#) on the STScI web site.

2 Mission Overview

2.1 Observatory architecture

Unlike the Hubble Space Telescope (HST), JWST will not be serviceable as it will be located 1.5 million kilometers away from Earth at the second Lagrange point so that the Observatory may always follow the Earth on its orbit. As shown in [Figure 1](#), the telescope will always be protected from the Sun, Earth and Moon by a five-layer sunshield approximately the size of a tennis court which will allow the telescope and its instruments to cool down passively to ~ 40 K. The 6.5m primary mirror is made of 18 hexagonal gold-coated beryllium segments. The Observatory includes four science instruments plus a Fine Guidance Sensor, all located on the back of the primary mirror in the Integrated Science Instrument Module (ISIM). The primary mirror, together with ISIM, constitute the Optical Telescope Element (OTE). Solar panels, the spacecraft, and a communication antenna are located on the warm (85°C) side of the Observatory. The whole Observatory is too large to be launched in its normal configuration; it will thus be folded at launch, like an origami figure, to fit the fairing of an Ariane 5 launcher which is one of ESA's contributions to the JWST project.

The deployment sequence, initiated immediately after launch, will last 14 days. Commissioning activities follow for a period of six months after launch in which all mirror segments are phased and all instrument modes tested and characterised. The mission is designed to last at least 5 years with a maximum of 11 years, limited by the propellant needed to keep the Observatory in its orbit.

Figure 1: Left: architecture of the JWST Observatory fully deployed. Right: view of the JWST completely assembled with its two halves — the Optical Telescope Element and the spacecraft element which includes the folded sunshield — together.

2.2 Mission status

The Observatory is currently in its final phases of integration. A major milestone was reached in September 2019 when the two halves of the Observatory, the OTE and the spacecraft element, were finally joined together. The Observatory will soon undergo a deployment sequence rehearsal as well as functional and environmental (vibration) tests. The Observatory will then be stowed into its launch configuration and delivered to Kourou in French Guyana in early 2021. The launch date is currently scheduled for the end of March 2021.

2.3 Science Planning Timeline

The commissioning period will include time to test all four science instruments including taking some representative images/spectra for each. These very first JWST data will be released soon after commissioning as part of the Early Release Observations (EROs) program. Cycle 1 science operations will begin in priority with Early Release Science (ERS) programs for a total of 500 hours as part of the Director Discretionary Time. The goal of ERS observations is to rapidly release data to the community with no proprietary period, demonstrate the scientific capabilities of JWST and test out all the instrument modes.

All four instrument teams and 6 interdisciplinary scientists have Guaranteed Time Observations (GTO) whose execution will begin in Cycle 1 with the restriction that no more than half of Cycle 1 Observations be allocated to GTO programs. The remaining time is for PI-driven General Observation (GO) programs. Both GO and GTO programs have a default proprietary period of 12 months.

Similarly to HST, GO proposals will be submitted annually to an international Time Allocation Committee (TAC). Canada is guaranteed at least 5% of the GO time (averaged over the long term) plus 450 hours of GTO for the Canadian Instrument Science Team. Canada will have representatives on the TAC in proportion to its share. The call for Cycle 1 GO proposals will be issued 23 January 2020 with a deadline of 1 May 2020. Figure 2 illustrates the science timeline with important dates.

3 Science Instruments

JWST is a general-purpose observatory that can and will enable a wide range of scientific investigations with unprecedented sensitivity (see Figure 3). Its four science instruments are designed to meet the mission science requirements (see next section) that translate into numerous observing modes covering a wide wavelength coverage from 0.6 to 28 μm . Together, the four JWST science instruments provide the following observing modes: broad, medium and narrow-band imaging, high-contrast imaging (coronagraphy), aperture masking interferometry

Figure 2: JWST science planning timeline, showing important milestones for the first two observing cycles.

(high-angular imaging), single-object spectroscopy, multi-object spectroscopy, slitless spectroscopy, integral field spectroscopy, capability for observing moving targets (Solar System objects) and specialised modes to perform high-precision time series photometric and spectroscopic observations of bright stars.

The next section provides a brief description of each science instrument. The focal plane footprint of all JWST instruments is shown in Figure 4. JWST will allow parallel observing with two instruments simultaneously to maximise the scientific return.

3.1 FGS/NIRISS

The Fine Guidance Sensor (FGS) and the Near-Infrared Imaging and Slitless Spectrograph (NIRISS), included in the same instrument module, constitute the Canadian hardware contribution to the JWST project. While the FGS has no scientific function, it is a mission-critical subsystem to provide fine guiding for the Observatory. FGS is a panchromatic (0.6 to 5.0 μm) near-infrared camera with two redundant footprints on the sky. During all observations, one star is selected with the FGS field of view and its centroid is measured 16 times per second to feed a steering mirror within the OTE to keep the telescope accurately pointed on its target.

NIRISS is a near-infrared (0.6 to 5.0 μm) camera offering four observing modes: 1) Imaging with the same broadband filters as NIRCams (except for one: F070W), 2) Single-Object Slitless Spectroscopy (SOSS) specifically designed for atmospheric characterisation of exoplanets, 3) Wide-Field Slitless Spectroscopy (WFSS) that provides $R \sim 150$ slitless spectroscopy between 0.9 and 2.2 μm using two gratings with orthogonal orientations and 4) Aperture Masking Interferometry (AMI) that provides moderate ($< 10^4$) contrast at angular resolution between 0.1 and 0.4 arcsec with three median-band filters between 3.8 and 4.8 μm , a mode specifically designed for faint companion detection at very high angular resolution (a few λ/D at 4 μm).

3.2 NIRCams

The Near Infrared Camera (NIRCams) covers wavelengths 0.6 to 5.0 μm with imaging, coronagraphy, and grism slitless spectroscopy modes. NIRCams has two modules with adjacent fields of view, $2.2' \times 2.2'$ each. Each module uses a dichroic to observe simultaneously in a short wavelength channel (0.6–2.3 μm) and a long wavelength channel (2.4–5.0 μm), making NIRCams a very efficient instrument for multi-band surveys. NIRCams is provided

Figure 3: Photometric and spectroscopic sensitivity of JWST compared to other facilities.

Figure 4: Focal plane footprint of all JWST instruments.

by the University of Arizona.

3.3 NIRSpec

The Near Infrared Spectrograph (NIRSpec) is a multi-mode 0.6 to 5.3 μm spectrograph. It offers a range of dispersing resolutions from the low-resolution ($R \approx 100$) prism to moderate resolution ($R \approx 1000 - 3000$) gratings. NIRSpec has fixed slit, integral-field and multi-object spectroscopy modes. The microshutter assembly implements a configurable mask of a quarter of a million shutters that can be individually set to open or closed to obtain spectra of about one hundred objects simultaneously. NIRSpec is provided by ESA with detector and microshutter contributions from NASA.

3.4 MIRI

The Mid-Infrared Instrument (MIRI) provides imaging and spectroscopic observing modes over a unique wavelength range from 4.9 to 28.8 μm . MIRI has wide-field imaging with a range of broad and narrow filters and coronagraphic imaging with a classical Lyot coronagraph and a 4-quadrant phase mask. There is low resolution ($R \approx 100$) slit or slitless spectroscopy and moderate resolution ($R \approx 1000 - 3000$) integral-field spectroscopy. MIRI was developed through a collaboration between European and US partners.

4 Canadian Science Programs

JWST is a general-purpose observatory that will enable numerous science programs under the following four science themes (see [Gardner et al. \(2006\)](#) and JWST websites for more details):

- First light & Reionization
- Assembly of Galaxies
- Birth of Stars & Protoplanetary Systems
- Planets & Origins of Life

In this section we highlight three major Canadian-led science programs to be carried out during the first year of JWST science operations.

4.1 CANUCS

CANUCS (*CANadian NIRISS Unbiased Cluster Survey*) is a 200-hr GTO program of slitless spectroscopy and imaging of five massive galaxy cluster and ten parallel fields using the NIRISS low-resolution grisms, NIRCам imaging and NIRSpec multi-object spectroscopy. The primary goal is understanding the evolution of low mass galaxies across cosmic time. The resolved emission line maps and line ratios for many galaxies, some at resolution of 100 pc, will allow the determining of the spatial distribution of star formation, dust and metals. Other science goals include the detection and characterisation of galaxies within the reionization epoch, using multiply-imaged lensed galaxies to constrain cluster mass distributions and dark matter substructure, and understanding star-formation suppression in the most massive galaxy clusters. Figure 5 illustrates the vast improvement in slitless spectroscopy for JWST compared to HST to measure the properties of the most distant galaxies.

4.2 NEAT

NEAT (*NIRISS Exploration of the Atmospheric diversity of Transiting exoplanets*) is a 200-hr GTO program to obtain NIRISS Single-Object Slitless Spectroscopy transit and eclipse observations of a sample of 14 exoplanets

Figure 5: Left: HST WFC3 G141 grism observations of the most distant known galaxy at $z = 11$ (Oesch et al., 2016). Right: simulated observation of the same galaxy with NIRISS Wide-Field Slitless Spectroscopy with 20 hours of observing time (two grisms, 3 hours per filter).

that span the full available range of equilibrium temperatures (300–3000 K) and masses ($1 M_{\oplus}$ – $2 M_{\text{Jup}}$) for planets appropriate for atmospheric characterisation. This program will thus reveal the full diversity of short-period exoplanet atmospheres. These observations will also measure the abundance of the molecules and aerosols present in the exoplanets’ atmospheres and determine the vertical temperature structure of the hottest targets. These results will allow us to address fundamental issues such as the formation process and formation location of these close-in planets, the presence and characteristics of particulate clouds, and non-equilibrium chemistry effects that might be at play in their atmosphere.

Three of the NEAT targets are Earth-sized including at least one (TRAPPIST-1f) in the habitable zone; the goal is to make the very first detection of an atmosphere on such a small, rocky planet, which would then allow us to place the first constraints on the mean molecular weight—and hence bulk composition—of its atmosphere. As shown in Figure 6, NIRISS should be capable of detecting the spectral signature of water in TRAPPIST-1f assuming a cloud-free Earth-like atmosphere.

For one target, observations will be acquired continuously throughout a full orbital period to constrain its temperature-pressure profile as a function of longitude and study how heat is absorbed and redistributed in its atmosphere.

4.3 Radiative Feedback from Massive Stars

This is a 30-hr ERS program to observe the prototypical Photo-Dissociation Region (PDR), the Orion Bar, using NIRCAM, NIRSpec-IFU, and MIRI in imaging and IFU mode. The primary goal is to rapidly deliver “template data”, as well as data processing and analysis tools for PDRs, which will be crucial for JWST proposal preparation for both the Galactic and extragalactic communities. While PDRs have long been associated with H II regions/molecular clouds, all diffuse to dense interstellar medium (ISM) interfaces are PDRs and much of the emission to be observed with JWST comes from PDRs. Indeed, the IR spectra of massive star-forming regions, proto-planetary disk surfaces, the ISM of galaxies, galactic nuclei, starburst galaxies, and (Ultra-)Luminous IR Galaxies ((U)LIRGS) are dominated by PDR emission signatures.

JWST will resolve and directly observe, for the first time, the response of PDR gas to the penetrating far-ultraviolet (FUV) photons in its key zones: the ionization front and the H I/H₂ photodissociation front, at unprecedented spectral and spatial detail over the full 1–28 μm range (see Fig. 7). These data will enable the detailed study of the physical and chemical processes at play in PDRs and the photo-chemical evolution of large carbonaceous

Figure 6: Simulated transit spectroscopy observations with NIRISS SOSS of the Earth-sized, temperate exoplanet TRAPPIST-1f. The blue curve is the predicted atmospheric signal assuming a cloud-free Earth-like atmosphere. The black and green dots with error bars are simulated NIRISS data corresponding to four visits. The spectral signature of water is clearly detected. Simulation courtesy of Björn Benneke.

molecules and nanoparticles, and will test widely used theoretical models and extend them into the JWST era. These observations and analysis tools will serve as a reference for accurate diagnostics of unresolved PDRs such as proto-planetary disk surfaces or distant star-forming regions.

5 JWST: a Key Investment for Canadian Astrophysics

JWST is by far the largest, most expensive space astronomy project ever undertaken in Canada. JWST data will constitute a huge scientific leverage for the Canadian astronomical community since the Observatory has strong synergy with virtually all ground- and space-based facilities such as ALMA and forthcoming giant telescopes (GMT, TMT and E-ELT); it is not unreasonable to think that JWST will be contemporary with at least one of these.

The development of a project on the scale of JWST is not without technical and financial challenges, and Canada has had its fair share of those. JWST's cost growth in particular has put strong pressure on space agencies. In this context, the CSA should be commended not only for its continuing financial support to the project but also for its positive response to fund GTO, GO and ERS programs after launch in a funding model similar to NASA's. Indeed, CSA has agreed to provide \$5 million over 5 years after launch for community science support. Given the huge investments that JWST represents for Canada, the CSA should commit to supporting the entire potential length of the mission, up to 11 years.

After two decades of active development, the onus will soon be on the astronomical community to exploit this unique facility that will surely make history for all the scientific breakthroughs it will enable.

5.1 A National Outreach Strategy for JWST

As HST's successor, JWST has the potential of being as impactful on the general public's perception of space and astronomy as its predecessor. Multiple studies (Christian, 1999, 2004) looking at the HST's impact in the USA have

Figure 7: Zooming into a PDR. **a)** Multi-wavelength view of a Galaxy (M81): UV tracing massive stars (blue), optical light tracing H II regions (green), and PAH emission tracing PDRs (red). **b)** Sketch of a typical massive star-forming region (at a distance of 2 kpc). **c)** Zoom in on one of the numerous PDRs, showing the complex transition from the molecular cloud to the PDR dissociation front, the ionization front and the gas flow into the ionized region. Inserted is the ALMA molecular gas data of the Orion Bar, at a resolution of 1'' (dashed lines; [Goicoechea et al., 2016](#)). The inset shows a model of the structure of the PDR. The scale length for FUV photon penetration corresponds to a few arcsec. The beam sizes of ISO-SWS, Spitzer-IRS and JWST-MIRI are indicated. JWST will resolve the 4 key regions. Courtesy of JWST-ERS ID 1288.

demonstrated that the observatory “has wide name recognition and enjoys wide public support”. Furthermore, it has been shown to “contribute to the general public understanding of science in both formal and informal education areas”. Nearly three decades after its launch, HST continues to make headlines across both traditional and new media and dazzle the public with its brilliant views of the Universe. Even its difficult beginnings — recall that the telescope required servicing shortly after its launch to fix issues with its mirror — is now often spun as a compelling underdog story and proof of the global scientific community’s resilience and innovation. That being said, while the entire world has benefited from and enjoyed Hubble’s work, it has always been clear that it is a NASA-led mission with contributions from ESA.

Canadians are most familiar with the Canadian Space Agency’s astronaut program and, perhaps, satellite missions. As a whole, Canadians are unaware that Canadian astronomers rank first in the G7 in standard analyses of per capita impact. The JWST mission could represent a paradigm shift for CSA’s public image and for our nation’s astronomical heritage. Canadian citizens will soon be able to know that their tax dollars have gone towards humanity’s quest to better understand the Universe and our place in it, not to mention the numerous technological spin-offs

created from JWST innovation that will go on to impact society on a daily basis. All these remarkable discoveries and advancements will remain in the shadow, however, unless an effective EPO and communications strategy for JWST is developed and delivered over the entire lifetime of the mission. As such, we believe it imperative that both communications specialists and astronomers with science communication or EPO experience support the mission.

Initiatives that should be considered include frequent press releases for scientific discoveries and mission milestones, collaborations with both formal and informal education centres and organisations, traditional and on-line/social media coverage and visibility at conferences, science festivals and public events via booths and public talks. A full-time Outreach Coordinator for JWST over a 10-year mission would cost approximately 0.5% of CSA's total contribution to the mission — well below the LRP2010's recommendation of 1.5% of the project's budget being allocated to EPO activities. This relatively small cost would ensure that the Canadian public fully partake in the mission's success, that the Canadian Space Agency establish itself as a global player in the space astronomy field and that the Canadian astronomical community enjoy more visibility on the national and international stage. If CSA and Canadian astronomers wish to partake in future international collaborations for space telescope missions (e.g. CASTOR, WFIRST, LUVOIR, etc.) and secure the necessary funding to do so, it is essential that the JWST mission be strongly leveraged to gain the support of the Canadian public and key decision-makers and stakeholders alike (c.f. Ouellette et al.'s LRP2020 white paper, *Astronomy Advocacy and Engagement*, for more information on this topic).

6 Conclusions & Recommendations

The next decade will be marked by the launch of JWST and the incredible discoveries it will enable. The JWST project is a very important point of reference for its numerous lessons learned regarding the development of future flagship space missions. Both supporting this mission for its entire lifetime *and* ensuring that Canadian JWST science is shared with the public are imperatives. To do so, we propose the following recommendations:

- We recommend that the Canadian Space Agency maintains its financial support to the mission and Canadian science for the entirety of the observatory's lifetime.
- We recommend that the Canadian Space Agency and the Canadian astronomical community recognise the importance of EPO activities. More specifically, we recommend the funding from CSA of a full-time Outreach Coordinator for the entire JWST mission.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

JWST is poised to be the premier space-based astronomical observatory of the next decade. It will certainly lead to multiple groundbreaking discoveries.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

JWST will enable a wide range of science programs. Its four science instruments provide mode redundancy. No given science theme depends exclusively on one instrument.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Through its partnership, Canada will be guaranteed at least 5% of the observing time and privileged science access through its 450 hours of the GTO program.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Canadian JWST science will involve broad collaborations mostly with the United States and Europe. CSA will provide financial support for successful GO proposals as well as for GTO and ERS proposals.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Yes. The JWST project has contributed to Canada's high reputation and expertise for developing complex space hardware. JWST's science will constitute a huge leverage for using existing and future facilities such as giant telescopes and possible future space missions. JWST led to several [spin-off](#) in various medical and technological applications. The most relevant for Canada is the expertise acquired in infrared detector technologies that has spun-off the development of new ground-based state-of-the-art infrared instruments with strong Canadian leadership (e.g. GPI, SPIRou, NIRPS, GIRMOS).

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

This benefit can only be assessed after launch but one can hardly cost the incredible scientific discoveries that JWST will enable. Canada's science return (5% + GTO) is a real bargain given its investment of ~ 200 millions (estimated over a 10-yr mission) that represents less than ~2% of the total cost of JWST (~\$10B).

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

Nothing can mitigate the very unlikely but still possible scenario wherein JWST falls into the ocean at launch! JWST does not rely on one single instrument. Mode redundancy across the four instruments will maximise the mission lifetime. Further launch delay is a significant financial risk that could affect the development of future Canadian space astronomy projects, big and small.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

The JWST project was possible through an unprecedented coordinated effort from academia, industry and government agencies (CSA, NRC). JWST represents an incredible opportunity for HQP training and EPO. JWST is already employing a large workforce in Canada. It had brought expats back to Canada. Providing opportunities for Canadians to be employed internationally. Universities are hiring personnel that can leverage off the JWST opportunity.

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